

REHMĀNA-PRĀSĀDA—A CHAPTER ON
THE MUSLIM MOSQUE
FROM THE VRKṢĀRṆAVA

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It is surprising that though the Muslims had built large and magnificent mosques in Syria, Iraq, Iran, Turkey, Egypt and Spain, they have no written text on the construction of their sacred architecture. Except the universal law that the congregation would face the Kaba (in Mecca) in accordance with the Quranic injunction¹ and that the Qiblah would mark its direction, there are no 'prescribed' rules nor norms for its making. The Hindus, on the other hand, were very particular in this matter. The *śāstra* ('theory') closely followed the standardised form of *prayoga* ('practice') in India and they laid down principles for the construction of the temple (*prāsāda*) to the minutest detail. Extensive treatises like the *Bṛhat-saṁhitā*, *Śukra-nīti-sāra*, *Hayaśirṣa-Pañcarātra*, *Agni-purāṇa*, *Viṣṇu-dharmottara-purāṇa*, *Kāśyapa-silpa*, *Mayamata*, *Abhilaṣitārtha-cintamaṇi*, *Mānasollāsa*, *Mānasāra*, *Samarāṅgaṇa-sūtradhāra*, *Aparājita-ṛccha*, *Śilpa-ratna*, *Viśvakarma-prakāśa*, *Pramāṇa-mañjarī*, *Vāstu-sāra-prakarāṇa*, *Prāsāda-maṇḍana* and other texts on *silpa* which deal with all the applied fine arts, such as architecture, sculpture, iconography, iconometry and painting are available to us.

It is highly interesting that in accordance with their own classical way of looking at things, the Hindus laid down a *vāstu*-text on the construction of the mosque for the first time, around the middle of the 15th century. This was made in the Māru-Gurjara region, the subject being dealt with under the title *Rehmāna-prāsāda* ('the Temple of Rehmāna', viz., Allah) along with other temples like *Sūrya-prāsāda*, *Śiva-prāsāda* and *Jina-prāsāda*. The *Rehmāna-prāsāda* forms a chapter

1. *Sura* II, verse 144, "Turn then thy face in the direction of the sacred Mosque; wherever you are, turn your faces in that direction."

in a larger work entitled *Vṛkṣārṇava*² which is one of the three important Māru-Gurjara works on architecture written in the 15th century. Speaking about the different temples, the text lays down :

संन्यासीमठकर्मेषु अनास्तिककुटिरके ।

बौद्धार्हतकेशचं व ध्वांक्षश्च सपुत्रके (?) ॥३५॥

‘रहमाणप्रासादेषु’ संन्यासी सर्ववर्शने ।

सिद्धायतनतीर्थेषु ध्वांक्ष[श्च] तत्र निश्चलम् ॥३६॥

‘Use *dhvāṅkṣa* proportions in the construction of the *maṭhas* of the *saṁnyāsins*, the huts of the atheists and the *caityas* and *vlhāras* of the Buddhists and the Jinas ; likewise this standard should be used in the construction of the *Rehmāna-prāsāda* (mosque), and the residential structures of the *saṁnyāsins* and the *siddhas*.

The *Vṛkṣārṇava* is in the form of a dialogue between *Viśvakarmā* and his *manasaputra* *Jaya*.³ The latter having listened to the detailed enumeration of the *Vairajya* type of temples, palaces, houses, stepwells, wells, tanks and other water-devices, temples of *Brahmā*, *Viṣṇu*, *Śiva* and *Sūrya*, types of stones and the images made from them, reservoirs, temples of *Brāhmaṇa*, *Kṣatriya*, *Vaiśya* and *Śūdra* natures, urges upon the former to explain to him the nature, proportions, rhythm, form and types of the temple built by the Muhammedans under the *sāttvika-bhāva* (‘the sentiment of godly adoration’).

Viśvakarmā replies : “Their temple is called ‘*Rehmāna-suralaya*’ (‘abode of the god *Rehmāna*’, *i.e.*, Allah). There is no image (as idol-worship is prohibited) and there they worship, through *dhyana* (contemplation), the formless attributeless all-pervading Supreme God whom they call *Rehmāna* (Allah). After working out the *āya* and *vyaya*, the levelled ground should be marked into eight or ten parts

2. M.A. Dhaky, ‘Māru-Gurjara vāstu-śāstramān masjid-nirmāna-vidhi’ (Gujarati), *Swadhyaya*, 7. i, pp. 64-79; he refers to another text, the *Jayapracchā*, which contains an independent chapter on *Rehmāna-Prāsāda* (Mosque) and also casual references in connection with the making of lamp-posts, gurgoyles etc. None of these works has, however, been published so far and Dhaky’s paper is the only source of information in this connection.

3. The Sanskrit text (as given by Dhaky, *op. cit.*, pp. 78-79) is appended herewith, *Appendix* pp. 243-44.

according to *sūtra-pramāṇa*. If it is an *Ekāṅga-prasāda* (*ekāṅga*=single quadruple mosque as distinguished from *caturāṅga*=four-quartered mosque ?), it would have two arms (sides) (*i.e.*, on north and south) with the western side closed and the Qiblah with quoins on the sides marked out (in the centre). Internally, this part would have a beautiful Mihrab. The temple will invariably face East, *i.e.*, its main entrance would be in the eastern side; enclosing walls would be given on the north and south sides. Directions should be precisely calculated and the *prāsāda* should face exactly East (so that the Mihrab may be on the western side and the congregation may face the direction of the Kaba). The plinth would consist of series of *bhīṭṭa*, *upabhīṭṭa* and *pīṭha* (so as to be sufficiently high). All ornamentation should consist of floral designs only. Externally, instead of the plain wall, various projections should be given so as to provide a number of pleasing quoins (which would be crowned by pinnacles); *chajjas* should be provided to protect all external sides as well as the (sanctuary and) *dalans*, over which (*i.e.*, on the superstructure) *chatris* should be arranged in series of two, three or five. Ornamental arched niches should be carved on the walls. There should be medallions containing rosettes on the facades between the pillars; all facades should be composed of arches supported on pillars. The Mihrab would consist of two parts (?)⁴ with pillars on its sides; the entrance portal would have three parts (?). The Qibla wall would be entirely closed. In all, the pillars would be used in seven parts of the *prāsāda* (?) and they would bear only the floral designs (consisting of flowers and leaves)."⁵

This prescription lays down the following fundamental requirements of the mosque forum :

- i. *It would face east* so that the Qiblah marking the direction of the Kaba could be provided on the western side. This is in accordance with the Quranic injunction which ordains the believers to face the Kaba while offering Namaz. The main entrance would, accordingly, be given in the eastern side.

4. Quite a few points of this account are not intelligible; they are marked with the sign of interrogation.

5. This translation differs in a large measure from the Gujarati translation of M.A. Dhaky (*cf.*, *op. cit.*, pp. 66-67); in fact, the text is fragmentary and the gaps have been filled on the basis of the specimens which were then in vogue in the 15th century in North India.

- ii. There would be no image and, instead, the Mihrab would be given in the centre of the western wall, facing which the believers would stand to worship their *nirañjana* and *nirakara* god through contemplation (*i.e.*, without rituals).

There are specific injunctions for making the Mihrab :

- iii. It would have a *high plinth*.
- iv. There would be *dalans* on the sides.
- v. *Pillars* would be used in its construction and particularly the arches of the facades would be supported on pillars.
- vi. Only *floral designs* would be used in its ornamentation and no sculptures or animate figures would be employed.

This *śāstra* is true to the extant examples except for two vital points, *viz*, (i) that no domes to superimpose the mosque, nor (ii) minars to flank the central arch of the facade, or to flank the facade on sides, have been mentioned. But the available text is incomplete and it is quite likely that these matters were dealt with in the later portion which has not come down to us.

The prescriptions given are strictly in accordance with the Islamic tenets and, it is certain, the text was written when the mosque had become a popular feature on the Indian scene and its numerous examples were available to the *śāstra-kāra* for making out a standardised version of the structure and laying down uniform norms and rules for its construction. It is a unique characteristic of the art of India that as soon as *prayoga* ('practice') is standardised through usage and evolution, its *śāstra* ('theory') is invariably written down for bringing about uniformity in the style and also for putting restraints and limitations to the possible reckless tendencies of the builders to take their own initiative, not caring for standard injunctions and norms of beauty.

It is pertinent to consider here as to what prompted the Hindus to lay down the principles for constructing the mosque lest it was built in a wrong way. The explanation is simple. Guilds of the Hindu artisans (*salats* or *silāwats*) were constantly employed on the construction of mosques and they treated this subject technically over and above any possible religious bias. They would worship the *Vastu-puruṣa* at the time of laying the foundation of the mosque as they would normally do in case of the temple and follow all other rituals of their own,

irrespective of the concurrence of their patron which might not have been available to them. Their art—whether it was used for making the temple or the mosque—was their *dharma* and was an entirely technical matter for them. The text was prepared at their behest by the Brāhmaṇa ācārya to provide technical knowledge on the subject as soon as its perfectly standardised form evolved after long experimentation.

Religious bias, in fact, was never there in Indian art. The caves of Ellora are identical, though their sectarian affiliations, Jaina, Buddhist and Brahmanical, are different. Indian art deals with its subject dispassionately and technically. The same set of building principles, plan, elevation, structural contrivances and ornamental themes governed the construction of temples of Jaina atheists and Vaiṣṇava theists at Khajuraho and, except for a few iconographic details, the temples of the former resemble those of the latter. Like the artisan, the *śāstrakāra* suffered from no taboos and dealt with the architecture of Jaina and Vaiṣṇava temples together in the same work. This phenomenon of Indian art depicts its amazing capacity to accept and assimilate extraneous inspirations and to adapt itself dynamically to changed conditions and situations.

The mosque was the sacred forum of the ruling people as well as a large section of the urban subjects and a fact in the Indian socio-religious order around the middle of the 15th century. Naturally, the subject of its architecture was admitted into the *Śilpa-śāstras* in accordance with the basic spirit of Indian thought which has been expressed by Vātsyāyana in the *Kama-sūtra* :

शास्त्रार्थान् व्यापिनो विद्यात् प्रयोगांस्त्वेकदेशिकान् । (2.9.41)

The nature of *śāstra* is universal, *i.e.*, all-embracing, while *prayoga* is only local. It is noteworthy that they laid down prescriptions for the construction of the mosque only, and not for the construction of the Tomb (Maqbarā) which largely depended on individual taste and choice and also on the financial capacity of the patron.

That the Hindus made a *śāstra* for the construction of masjid is a fact of great significance, especially because it is representative of the trend of cultural rapprochement which had developed under the provincial dynasties in Mewar, Gujarat, Malwa, Gwalior, Jaunpur, Bengal and Kashmir and bore fruits under the more congenial reign of the Mughals about a century later.

Appendix

श्रीरहमाणप्रासादलक्षणम्

जयोवाच—

प्रासादानां च हे तात ! वास्तुशास्त्रविशारद ।
 श्रुता मया तु प्रासादा वैराज्यकुलसम्भवाः ॥ १ ॥
 राजवेश्मगृहादि च त्वया प्रोक्तं सुविस्तरम् ।
 वापीकूपतडागाद्यं चारुणं विविधं पुनः ॥ २ ॥
 प्रासादा अपि ते सर्वे गणादिनां यथाक्रमम् ।
 ब्रह्मविष्णुशिवाकार्णां कथिता विविधालयाः ॥ ३ ॥
 शल्यावीनां च सर्वेषां तेषामर्चा अनेकशः ।
 कथिताः करुणासिन्धो ! श्रुता अपि मया पुनः ॥ ४ ॥
 ब्रह्मक्षत्रियविद्शूद्राश्चत्वारप्रकृत्योत्तमाः ।
 सात्त्विकं भावमपन्ना कारयन्ति सुरालयान् ॥ ५ ॥
 म्लेच्छरूपेण विख्याता ये लोका म्लेच्छरूपिणः ।
 तेषां सात्त्विकभावश्चेत् कथं कुर्यात् सुरालयम् ॥ ६ ॥
 तस्य छन्दस्तदाकारं मण्डपं द्वारसंस्थितम् ।
 प्रमाणाद्यं समस्तं मे कथयस्व जगत्प्रभो ॥ ७ ॥

श्री विश्वकर्मा उवाच—

शृणु पुत्र प्रयत्नेन सर्वशास्त्रविशारद ।
 साधु पृच्छन्ति तन्नाम 'रहमाण'सुरालयम् ॥ ८ ॥
 तत्र ध्यायन्ति यवनाः देवरूपविवर्जितम् ।
 मायासंसर्गरहितं गुणत्रयविवर्जितम् ॥ ९ ॥
 निरञ्जनं निराकारं तानेकमयमद्भुतम् ।
 तद्ध्यानकं × × पुत्र ! रहमाणं विदुर्बुधाः ॥ १० ॥
 चतुरश्रं समं कुर्यादायव्ययविशोधितम् ।
 भाजयेदष्टभिर्मागिर्दशभिर्वापि सूत्रतः ॥ ११ ॥
 भुजद्वयं प्रकर्तव्यमेकाङ्गं कोणभङ्गयुक् ।
 भित्तिबाह्ये प्रकर्तव्यं मिहिरावं मनोहरम् ॥ १२ ॥

पूर्वमुखं प्रकर्तव्यं अप्रशस्तं च विकत्रये ।

सूत्रेण साधयेद्भित्तिं मीयतां दक्षिणोत्तरे ॥ १३ ॥

ध्रुवेन शङ्कुना चापि प्राचीं यत्नेन साधयेत् ।

दिङ्मूढं नैव कर्तव्यं कर्तव्यं पूर्वसम्मुखम् ॥ १४ ॥

भिट्टोपभिट्टपीठं च सर्वोपरि च विन्यसेत् ।

पुष्पकं पुष्पसंयुक्तं ऊर्ध्वे मण्डोवरं वरम् ॥ १५ ॥

प्रासादछन्द एकाङ्गो बहिः कोणाद्यलंकृतः ।

ऊर्ध्वे फांसाऽऽकृतियंस्य रहिमानः स उच्यते ॥ १६ ॥

वीथिकायां ततो विक्षु ससूत्रं कपिशीर्षकम् ।

द्वित्रिपञ्चक्षणोपेतं तदूर्ध्वे मालिकां न्यसेत् ॥ १७ ॥

अधःस्थाने वैष्णव्यं महिराबं मनोहरम् ।

स्तम्भके सम्मुखे तत्र तन्मध्ये पुष्पकं वरम् ॥ १८ ॥

महिराबं द्विभागोऽथ स्तम्भकोभयपार्श्वयोः ।

त्रिभागं तु प्रवेशेन पृष्ठदेशे समांशकम् ॥ १९ ॥

सप्तभागा स्थिताः स्तम्भाः पुष्पकैश्च विभूषिताः ।

तद्वदे(?)लम्बि ॥ २० ॥